

POLITICAL RELATIONS BETWEEN IRAN AND PAKISTAN FROM 1947 TO 1978

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Abstract

Iran and Pakistan, having wide and common borders, have always played an important role in international and regional developments. In 1326/1947, Pakistan was separated from India, an independent country with special laws and policies was formed. Accordingly, this country needed to have allies in the region and the world to strengthen its national security. At the same time, in Iran, the government of Mohammad Reza Shah took measures to strengthen its foreign relations to establish relations with its neighbors. Pakistan was one of these countries that had political, commercial and cultural relations and agreements with each other during the Pahlavi period. This research examines and analyzes the political relationship between the two countries of Iran and Pakistan based on the descriptive-analytical method and the method of collecting library information and based on historical documents. The purpose of this research is to clarify the political relations of these two countries in the field of academic studies. The main question is, how were the political relations between these two countries during the Pahlavi period. According to the findings and documents, the current research can argue that during the Pahlavi period and during the time of Mohammad Reza Shah, Iran had a good political relationship with Pakistan.

Keywords: Iran, Pakistan, Foreign Relations, Political Relations, Baghdad Pact.

INTRODUCTION

The history of Iran's civilizational, historical and cultural links with the Indian subcontinent reaches more than thousands of years, but the historical record of Iran's political relations with a country called Pakistan is very short-lived. The end of the colonial era and the beginning of the wave of independence movements in the third world led to the creation of new political entities in the political geography of the world, of which the division of the Indian subcontinent and the formation of the country of Pakistan in August 1947 are among the most important. Based on long-standing cultural and civilizational relations and religious commonalities centered on Islam, as well as the specific political considerations of the Cold War era, the Kingdom of Iran was the first country in the world to recognize the independence of Pakistan on August 14, 1947. The relations between the two countries developed rapidly based on the aforementioned factors, especially the political, cultural and civilizational links. As Burke and Zairing point out, Pakistan's continuous interest in Iran stems from the fact that Iran, as its immediate neighbor, is also considered the father of Pakistani culture. (Bork and Zairing, 2009: 491). The relations between the two countries, due to the closeness of the policies of the imperial government of Iran and the government of Pakistan regarding bilateral and regional issues, including India and Afghanistan, as well as alignment with the policies of the United

States, especially in the form of the Sento Pact, until the victory of the Islamic Revolution in Iran, are at a very high level. It was favorable. The starting point of political relations between Tehran and Islamabad goes back to the period of independence of Pakistan from India on August 14, 1947. After the declaration of Pakistan's independence, Iran was the first country to recognize the establishment of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, and this is a turning point in the relations between the two countries. Parallel to the opening of the Iranian embassy in Karachi (the capital of Pakistan at that time), on October 24, 1947, Mohammad Reza Pahlavi, the former Shah of Iran, was the first head of state to visit this country after the independence of Pakistan in 1949. Also, Iran was the first country to sign the Treaty of Maudt with Pakistan on August 14, 1956. In this research, the political relations between Iran and Pakistan are analyzed based on the available documents. A research has been done around this topic and in the field of relations between these two countries as the background of this research. Among others, we can mention the following: "History of Pakistan's Foreign Relations" by Burke and Zairing, is one of the works that deals with Pakistan's foreign relations and foreign policies. In this book, the author evaluates the role of Iran in the consolidation of power in Pakistan as very important, but at the same time, he did not dedicate a chapter to Iran, but during the discussions of this book, the role of Iran can also be understood. Another work in the field of foreign relations between the two countries under discussion is an article titled "Iran-Pakistan Relations: America's Role" written by Samitar Kumar. In this article, the author considers the United States to be the most important factor in the relationship between Iran and Pakistan, and most of its discussions are in the field of relations between the two countries facing the American government and the Caspian Sea area. A collection of articles has also been published in the field of foreign relations between the two countries written by Tayyaba Vaezi, which refers to the investigation of various issues with a descriptive perspective between Iran, Pakistan and Afghanistan. Another article that is necessary to mention is written by Harsh Pant entitled "Dysfunctional relations between Iran and Pakistan" in which the author analyzes the differences between Iran and Pakistan on various military and religious issues, the presence of the Taliban and Afghanistan and NATO has discussed. In this article, the main reason for the difference between the two countries is the interests of Shia and Sunni sects. "Assessment of Border Threats in Southeast Iran" by Masoud Hosseini and Abbas Alipour (2013), is another article that mostly refers to the regional threats of neighboring countries and is a general discussion about regional threats. Another article titled "Geostrategic analysis of Iran-Pakistan relations with an emphasis on the security factor" by Mohammad Jafar Arjamand and Arash Bidullah Khani (2013), which is actually the framework of the said article is about the military situation of these two countries. There is no mention of political relations between the two. As the history of the research shows, many books and articles examine the relations between Pakistan and Iran from a military and security point of view, and none of these works mention political relations in a methodical and documented manner with political documents and Administration has not been analyzed. Therefore, in the current research, an attempt is made to open a new window to the political relations between Iran and Pakistan based on new documents and findings.

History of Iran-Pakistan relations

The Islamic Republic of Pakistan was separated from India in 1947/1326 after the continuous efforts of Indian Muslims under the leadership of Quaid-e-Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah and became an independent country. After independence, Pakistan was divided into eastern (Bangladesh) and western (now Pakistan). But in 1971, its eastern part was separated from the western part and Pakistan was limited only to West Pakistan. (Mukhtar, p. 28) Deep relations between Pakistan and Iran originate from their common language, history and culture. These relationships can now be seen in Pakistan with classical Persian poetry in many contemporary buildings. The friendly relations of these two countries go back to 1947 and the division of the subcontinent. Therefore, Iran and Pakistan soon entered into strong relations in political, economic and even cultural fields and established comprehensive cooperation. In this regard, an official friendship and cooperation agreement was signed between the two countries in 1950. (Zahid Ali Khan, 2004: 169) Following the long period of Cold War, both countries remained united and were strategically aligned during the Pahlavi II era. In addition, Pakistan was the first country to recognize the Islamic Revolution of Iran. In 1980, during the Iran-Iraq war, despite the great pressure on Pakistan to support Iraq, Pakistan explicitly declared its support for Iran. Today, both countries are making serious efforts to overcome destructive factors and elements whose aim is to darken the relations between the two countries. Therefore, both sides are seriously committed to examining mutual economic fields, including trade and gas pipeline projects. Iran is very important for an energy-deficient country like Pakistan due to its rich natural resources of oil and gas. Having said that, Pakistan and Iran are two neighboring countries that not only share a common border, but also have many commonalities in terms of linguistic, economic, social and historical, ethnic, cultural and religious relations. Ethnically, the people of Iran and Pakistan both belong to the Aryan race (Ahmadi, 2014: 123).

Religious relations, especially Shia and Sufi tendencies in Iran, have attracted the hearts of the Shia masses of Pakistan and a sense of closeness between them. Apart from these relations, the governments of the two countries have maintained cooperation and reliable relations for a long time due to the hundred-year-old networks and trade routes. It can be said that Iranian culture has deeply shaped Pakistani clothing, music, poetry and architecture. In addition, until the rise of the British Empire in India, Persian continued to be the official communication tool of the Mughal Empire. Therefore, great poets such as Hafez, Molavi, Saadi, Khayyam and other poets influenced the Persian language and poetry in Urdu, which is the official language of Pakistan (Akram, 1968: 33). Therefore, the political support of Iran by the Indian Muslims indicated a deeper connection between the two Muslim communities. In 1940, the Muslim League approved a resolution in favor of Reza Shah Pahlavi during the occupation of foreign forces. After the independence of Pakistan in 1947, Iran was the first country to accept this newly established country and defend its rights against Hindus. The Constitution of Pakistan was approved and implemented in 1949 based on the Quran and Sunnah. (Safdar, 1991: 44) Pakistan's relations with Iran have different stages, some of which have been successful and others have failed. But these diplomatic failures did not damage the relations between the two countries. During the years 1947 to 1965, Pakistan was able to have successful relations with the countries of the Islamic world, including Iran. In 1964, proper relations between Iran and

Pakistan were established due to their membership in SENTO. And with the formation of RCD (Rafique Najma, 2016: 222) in 1964 by Pakistan and the membership of Iran and Turkey, the relations between them deepened. These good relations indicate Iran's sincere efforts to resolve the 22-month crisis between Pakistan and Afghanistan in April 1960. The only problem between the two countries that suddenly arose was the settlement of the border problems between the two countries. However, two governments successfully solved this problem in 1967 (Surrender Chopra, 1974: 310). During the war between India and Pakistan in 1965, Iran joined Turkey to support Pakistan. Two years later, Pakistan defended Iran's policies in order to support the Arab world against Israel. Arranged (Qureshi, 1968: 79).

In the late 1960s, there were disturbances in Pakistan, which led to its partition in 1971. And this division had caused the political weakness of Pakistan. During this period, due to England's withdrawal from the Suez Canal, Iran gained strength. The oil embargo in 1973 strengthened Iran's role in the region while Britain was trying to dominate the region. Pakistan and Iran had good relations in this decade.

Common areas of political relations

The common issues between Iran and Pakistan and having many commonalities between the people who live on both sides of the borders of these countries have caused a deep level of relations between the two countries. Iran's interaction with Pakistan has had special capacities and abilities. Here, the factors that have caused the consistency and expansion of the political relations between the two countries between 1947 and 1979 are examined.

Common History

Pakistan dates back to at least 2500 years BC with the remains of the Indus Valley Civilization in Mohenjo-daro and Harappa and other archaeological excavations. In fact, the history of Pakistan is not separate from the history of the Indian subcontinent, and whenever the history of Pakistan is discussed, the name of the Indus Valley civilization, the arrival of the Aryans to this region, and a part of the ancient history of India, will inevitably be at the top of the chapter of Pakistan's history. The point that should be noted here is that the cultural relations between Iran and Pakistan and Iran and the subcontinent are two separate issues. Because the relations between Iran and India today started when the Muslims conquered Delhi in the 7th and 8th centuries AH and made it their capital, and then the Islamic monarchy spread from there to other parts of the subcontinent. But the relations between Iran and the Indus Valley, or the region that is called Pakistan today, are very old. These two lands have always had close ties. Iranians did not have access to present-day India, whose official name is "Bharat", and their only travel was to Western India, which was called the Indus Valley (Pakistan). Throughout the history of every political, cultural, religious and religious change that has occurred in Iran, after a short period of time, its results and effects have been seen in the land of Pakistan (Chaudhry, 1996: 413). These two lands are sometimes under one government and sometimes separate but In any case, they have had very close relations. Throughout history, these relations have never been broken. What is called Pakistan today has been under the influence of Iranian culture and politics more than other regions in the Indian subcontinent (Shafi'i, 2017: 25).

Common Border

Although Afghanistan, India and China also share borders with Pakistan, the neighborhood with Iran has a superior position for Pakistan. Because this border has always been a border of friendship and peace for that country. In other words, Pakistan and Iran have always benefited more from these privileges due to their neighborhood, and more importantly, Iran has always been known as the father of Pakistani culture. After independence, India lost its long-standing closeness and territorial proximity with Iran, and instead, Pakistan became Iran's neighbor with a common border of about 590 miles (830 kilometers). Iran, which itself suffered a lot from the injuries of World War II, is living in the first years of Pahlavi II's rule. The Shah, who was struggling with many domestic, regional and global political and economic problems, seized the opportunity and was the first country to recognize Pakistan after independence and established diplomatic relations with that country in June 1326/1947. established This border with people on both sides of the border who have a common ethnicity, religion, language, clothing and culture, and also the unsettled relations between the two countries with their other neighbors are effective factors in expanding and emphasizing the common culture between the two countries between 1947 and 1947. It was until 1979.

Common Religion

Islam came to India by three important factors: 1) by Arab merchants who traveled to Gujarat and Deccan 2) by Muhammad bin Qasim Thaqfi 3) in the 10th and 11th centuries, Turkish and Afghan rulers attacked India with the intention of jihad. But these three factors have played a small role in its spread and sometimes it has even caused Hindus to stand against Muslims (Arshad, 2000: 211). They converted to Islam. The conflict between Hindus and Muslims started when Islam came to India as a conqueror and a swordsman. Abu Rayhan Biruni writes in this regard: "Sultan Mahmud fought with Hindus for thirty-odd years and destroyed the land of India. The remnants of the Indians who remained, were completely hostile and obstinate with the Muslims" (Biruni, 1983: 13). With the arrival of Islam, the inhabitants of the Indian subcontinent were forever divided into two completely different societies, and two nations continued to live in this land with two distinct cultures and characteristics that made their mixing and blending impossible (Walyan, 1998): 5) until in 1947, these two societies officially created two independent countries, India and Pakistan. In fact, the real history of Pakistan begins with the arrival of Islam in this land.

The export of Islam to the Indo-Pure land, through Iran, and especially through the Sufis, whose names have remained in the religious-mystical culture, has created a special bond between these two countries (Arafi, 2013: 42), it can be boldly said that Islam The intense interest of Pakistani Muslims in Islam, the historical unity and the intermingling of the Muslim areas with Iranians from the earliest days have been among the factors of the expansion of political and cultural relations between the two countries between 1947 and 1979. To the extent that the Shah was the first leader who visited Pakistan in February 1328, 1950, and his visit to Pakistan was highlighted by the fact that the two countries were Muslim (Information Newspaper, 12/25/1328), while Pakistan considered Iran as a shortcut. He knew how to communicate with the Islamic world. (Waazi, 2010: 20).

The migration of Iranian families to the Indian subcontinent

With the arrival of Islam in India, vast political, social and cultural changes appeared there. After the attack of Sultan Mahmud of Ghaznavi and the formation of the Muslim dynasties from 602-932 A.H., it lasted for 3 centuries ago, it caused great mystical personalities such as Mirysid Ali Hamdani, Ali bin Othman Hajwayri Saheb Kashf al-Mahjub and Khwaja Moin al-Din Chishti to India migrated and not only created tremendous effects in that land, but also provided suitable grounds for the migration and travel of many masters of grace, art and literature.

Three groups of immigrants migrated from Iran to India. 1) The first group were people of knowledge and writing. 2) The second group were mystics and Sufis. 3) The third group were those who were greedy and greedy. They moved to this country.

There are several reasons for the migration of Iranians to India. Kiyomarth Amiri divides these factors into two categories:

- 1) The reasons that sent Iranians to India willingly and voluntarily. Such as the abundance of blessings, suitable areas for business, the spread of Islam, the art education of Muslim sultans and princes, and the confirmation of government officials.
- 2) The reasons that forced Iranians to migrate, such as the chaos and instability of the political, social and economic situation, the invasion of the Mongols, the harshness of the kings and local rulers, the Safavid sultans' disregard for poetry and politeness, and the extreme religious fanaticism of some Safavid and Seljuk sultans. (Amiri, 1994: 108).

The Safavid era is the era of large-scale migration of Iranian poets to the territory of Gurkans of India and the Deccan, which led to the prosperity of Persian poetry and the spread of Iranian culture and the Persian language in India. These migrations began during the reign of Shah Tahmasab I Safavid and reached its peak during the reign of Jalaluddin Muhammad Akbar. Ismaili Muslims. In 1843, after an unsuccessful rebellion against the Qajar rulers, the first Aga Khan moved from Iran to Bombay. His grandson, Sir Sultan Muhammad Shah or Agha Khan 3, became one of the founders and the first president of the All India Muslim League in 1908, and the movement finally established the independent and Muslim-majority country of Pakistan in 1947 (Pirzada, 1969: 49).

Nahid Afkhani, the daughter of Amir Taimur Kalali, the wife of the first president of Pakistan Jamur, and Nusrat Esfahani, Sir Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto (the news, 2011: 24 October) were prominent figures in Pakistani politics, after the declaration of independence of Pakistan and the separation of this country from India in 1947, along with others. The Muslims of the subcontinent settled in Pakistan and provided the means for the cultural fusion of the two countries of Iran and Pakistan. In fact, these Iranian immigrants are considered as cultural ambassadors of Iran in Pakistan, who brought a collection of customs, art, industry, literature, etc. to this country with them.

Political relations between Iran and Pakistan in the second Pahlavi era

The starting point of political relations between Tehran and Islamabad goes back to the historical stage of Pakistan's independence from India on August 14, 1947. It was mentioned earlier that after the declaration of independence of Pakistan, Iran was the first country to recognize the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, and this is a turning point in the relations between the two countries. In 1949, the Shah of Iran was the first head of state to visit Pakistan after independence. According to the political events in this period, Iran-Pakistan relations in three levels; we examine mutual, tripartite and international relations.

Mutual relations:

The strategic and geographical position as well as the common history were among the important factors that brought these two countries closer to each other after the independence of Pakistan. Meanwhile, Iran was the first country that supported Pakistan's entry into the United Nations. He also supported Pakistan's position on the Kashmir issue inside and outside the United Nations. During this period, Iran also announced its agreement to resolve border issues between itself and Pakistan under the supervision of the United Nations. This was while most of the Muslim countries refused to comment on the conflict between India and Pakistan on the Kashmir issue, but at this time, Iran was the only Muslim country that supported Pakistan in this regard. Moreover, Pakistan's decision to befriend Iran was in response to its strained relations with its close neighbors, India and Afghanistan. In fact, cooperation with Iran seemed necessary for the position of Pakistan's defense strategy, therefore Pakistan's strategic, political, economic and security needs brought it closer to Iran. But apart from these political and security considerations, the role of religion cannot be ignored. Pakistan considered Iran's friendship as a turning point in the path of the unity of the Islamic world. During his first visit to Pakistan in March 1950, the Shah of Iran said in his speech, "The government and people of Iran are pleased with the establishment of a new Islamic state in their neighborhood and this gives him an opportunity to convey the friendly feelings of the Iranian nation personally and directly. Tell his Pakistani brothers" (Qureshi, 1968: 34)

According to Pakistan, Iran is a country with a special strategic position and a common history and religion, which is actually an important factor in the good relations between the two countries. Therefore, Iran is a key element in Pakistan's foreign policy. Pakistan believes that maintaining cordial relations with Iran is necessary for the economic prosperity and security of the region. Pakistan's close relations with Iran are very important not only for both countries but also for the region.

Iranian leaders visit Pakistan

Mohammad Reza Shah's first trip to Pakistan lasted from March 10 to March 25, 1949. The Prime Minister of Pakistan, Liaquat Ali Khan and the Cabinet of Ministers of Pakistan welcomed him, the trip started with a magnificent party organized by the Prime Minister of Pakistan, and during the next days of the trip, the Shah visited the tomb of Muhammad. Ali Jinnah went to the Pakistan Navy, the Iran-Pakistan Cultural Association, the Royal Pakistan Air Force, the Officers' College in Quetta and the historic sites of Lahore, Peshawar, Risalpur,

and also made short trips to the eastern regions of Pakistan, present-day Bangladesh, and the northwestern borders of Pakistan. The two-week official visit of the Shah of Iran ended on March 25, 1949.

On March 17, 1955 A.H., after his visit to India, the Shah of Iran made a one-day visit to Pakistan for the second time and was welcomed by the Prime Minister of Pakistan, Mohammad Ali Chaudhry, and the people of Karachi. On March 18, a cultural contract was signed between Iran and Pakistan in Karachi, based on which the two countries could exchange students, teachers, teachers, and cultural and sports teams. (Vatanka, 2015:19)

Mohammad Reza Shah's third trip to Pakistan took place on 20 February 1959. The Shah of Iran along with Queen Farah Pahlavi arrived in Karachi at the invitation of Field Marshal (General) Ayub Khan, President of Pakistan and were welcomed by him. During this trip, Turkish President Jalal Bayar went to Karachi from Ankara to participate in the talks with the Shah of Iran and Ayub Khan. During this trip, the Shah of Iran visited the new building of the Imperial Cobra Embassy and met with Iranians living in Karachi. After Karachi, he went to Lahore, where he participated in the fifth anniversary of the Sento Treaty. In this ceremony, a statement was published by the leaders of Iran, Turkey and Pakistan. On March 7, 1960, the Shah's trip to Pakistan ended and he flew to Abadan along with Turkish President Jalal Bayar.

Mohammad Reza Shah's fourth trip to Pakistan took place on July 9, 1963. In this four-day trip, the Shah of Iran traveled to Rawalpindi to meet and talk with the President of Pakistan. Marshal Ayub Khan and other high-ranking officials of the country came to the airport to welcome the Shah.

In this trip, apart from the common issues of the two countries and mutual cooperation, the Iran-Pakistan trade agreement, which was approved in Tehran on 20 May 1962 AD, was implemented... After a four-day visit to Pakistan, the Shah of Iran returned to Tehran. In the joint statement of Iran and Pakistan that was published on the occasion of this meeting, it was noted that the leaders of the two countries have discussed the issues of the two countries and the ways of interdependence and alignment in their views. Also, during this statement, the Shah of Iran announced his readiness to mediate to remove the obstacles and differences between the two countries of Pakistan and Afghanistan.

The fifth trip of Mohammad Reza Shah was carried out on 8th of February 1963. This visit was aimed at establishing closer and more friendly cooperation between the two countries of Iran and Pakistan. This trip started with Ayub Khan and his cabinet and MPs welcoming the Shah of Iran at the Rawalpindi airport. During this trip, he visited Varsk Mangala Dam, which was the largest dam in Pakistan.

On the third day of this meeting, the Shah of Iran along with Ayub Khan entered Lahore, after visiting the military exercise, they participated in the "Conference of Asian and African Thinkers" and visited Lahore University. Foreign Minister Bhutto and West Pakistan Governor Amir Muhammad Khan were also present in this visit. The last visit of the Shah of Iran to Pakistan was made on March 15, 1967. (Qureshi, 1968: 33-34).

Pakistani leaders visit Iran

Mohammad Reza Shah's 32-year foreign policy regarding Pakistan and its ruling regimes constituted more than 80% of the life of his rule (1942-1979 AD), among which the share of the military governments of General Iskander Mirza, General Mohammad Ayub Khan, General Agha Muhammad Yahya Khan and General Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq were more, and the non-military governments of Pakistan were limited to the government of Muhammad Ali Jinnah and Zulfikar Ali Bhutto. The Shah himself was a military person and was interested in the military. (Zonis, 2010: 30-32) There is no detailed information about the visit of the first ruler of Pakistan, Liaqat Ali Khan. The first president of Pakistan, General Iskander Mirza, whose wife was Nahid Amir Taimur, daughter of Amir Taimur Kalali and of Iranian descent, spent the rest of his life in London after being expelled from Pakistan and died on November 13, 1969 due to a heart attack. The president of the time, Yahya Khan, prevented his burial in East Pakistan, Mohammad Reza Shah Pahlavi sent his private plane to London and the body of President Iskander Mirza was transferred to Tehran and during a ceremony attended by Iranian government officials and hundreds of Iranians. And Pakistani immigrants, his body was buried in Tehran.

After Iskander Mirza, General Ayub Khan came to work. He went to Tehran on 26 Mehr 1967 at the invitation of the king of Iran to see an air show. Babaei, Gholam Reza, 2014: 127).

After General Ayub Khan, General Yahya Khan visited Iran for the first time as president. (29 October to 4 November 1969) he visited military centers and participated in the 10th Aban exercise of the Air Force. (Journal of fifty years of the Pahlavi dynasty, 1985: 1872)

These bilateral relations reached such a stage of prosperity during Zulfikar Ali Bhutto's rule (1978-1972) that Zulfikar Ali Bhutto said in response: "Even in the world of imagination, the occurrence of any dispute or conflict between Iran and Pakistan is not imagined." (Yearbook of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 1973: 272)

During his rule, Zulfikar Ali Bhutto visited Iran 15 times, April 1974, Aban 1353, July 1976, and January 1976 (Documents and News of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, 1976: 37). He expressed his satisfaction and stated: "You have your constitution now, although I am a soldier and a soldier, I am happy that Pakistan is finally governed by a civilian government." (Tasbihi, 1973: 271)

After Zulfikar Ali Bhutto was dismissed and Ziaul Haq took office in September 1978 AD, he seized the opportunity and embarked on a one-day private trip to Iran and met with the Shah of Iran. During this meeting, bilateral issues of interest to the parties were discussed in a "warm and friendly atmosphere". (Nazeer Ahmed Irani, 1977, 89)

Bilateral contracts

Agreement of tenure 1950/1329 A.H

Iran takes the first step of friendship, the day after the recognition of Pakistan, the subject of the treaty included issues that were raised by that country since the beginning of Pakistan's independence. In the meeting he had with the officials of the Foreign Ministry of Iran on March

23, 1948, the Ambassador of Pakistan emphasized that two demands of his respective government should be met in line with the drafting of the agreement:

- 1) The agreement (before concluding it with India) should be concluded with Pakistan first.
- 2) to speed up its conclusion.

The response of the Iranian government officials was that: "We will consider the conclusion of such an agreement with open arms" (the text of the name dated 3/16/1950 of the Covenant and Legal Department) in the agreement, it was stated that the parties will establish political and consular relations based on the laws establish international relations and settle all their disputes of any kind in a friendly manner and in a suitable time through diplomatic channels and in a peaceful manner. The Moudat Treaty was based on 4 main articles, this treaty was signed on behalf of the Imperial Government of Iran, Dr. Ali Akbar Saasi, and on behalf of the Government of Pakistan, Ghazanfar Ali Khan, on 14th of February 1950 in Tehran (Archive of the Center for Diplomatic Records and History of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs), 1950: 284-1-19) The important points of this agreement are: 1) The parties establish permanent peace and friendship between Iran and Pakistan and between the nationals of the two countries in their respective countries, 2) Both sides maintain their political and consular relations. According to the international principles and the principle of the complete state of al-Wadad, 3) for closer proximity, the parties were decided to conclude other agreements such as commercial and customs agreements and the extradition of criminals, 4) the parties are obliged to resolve possible disputes through political and friendly channels and resolve peacefully (same: 284-1-19).

Agreement on border regulations 1959/1328 AH in Tehran

According to studies, a newly independent country usually has border disputes with neighboring countries, hence when Pakistan was formed it had border disputes with Burma, China, Iran, Afghanistan and India. Fortunately, in the case of the first three countries, namely Burma, China and Iran, all issues were resolved in a very fair manner.

In general, Pakistan's border policy is based on two principles:

- 1) Minimizing the source of risk to security and integrity from across borders
- 2) Creating smooth relations and cooperation with one's neighbors, which in turn requires goodwill, wisdom and flexibility in the approach of negotiations in the field of border disputes. (Murtaza Rizvi, 1971: 203)

Pakistan's common border with Iran, known as the Goldsmith Line, is about 590 miles long, extending from Mount Malik Sieh, the junction of Afghanistan, Iran and Pakistan, to the Gulf of Gwadar in the Oman Sea. Pakistan's border with Iran can be said to be a legacy of the British Empire, and some parts of Baluchistan were under the control of Iran before the emergence of the British legacy. After the conquest of Baluchistan in 1871, 1896 and 1905, Britain concluded border agreements with Iran, but the borders of Baluch Iran remained largely undefined. (The imperial gazetteer of India, 1908 vol 3, 265) For this reason and due to the confusion about the existing borders in the years 1947-1949, some minor border conflicts occurred which were not

serious enough to be reflected in the press. Therefore, neither Pakistan nor Iran have ever publicly commented on border issues. Some of the later conflicts occurred in the mid-1950s when Pakistan was trying to convince Iran to join the Pakistan-Turk Pact. And these conflicts could jeopardize the tripartite relationship of cooperation, which was publicly displayed by Rcd.

George Lenkoszki points out another fact that forces both countries to resolve their border disputes peacefully and quickly. This was a common problem between Iran and Pakistan, that is, a movement for national autonomy in Baluchistan, a province that has a common position in these two countries. (George Lenczowski: 219)

As a result, in 1955, at the suggestion of Pakistan, the two countries agreed to arbitrate their border problem in case of failure of direct negotiations between them. Therefore, an Iranian delegation came to Karachi in 1955 to review the border of the two countries. In July of the following year, the two governments agreed to appoint a joint commission also tasked with revising the Goldsmith's Line.

To speed up the determination of large-scale maps of the entire border areas, it clearly shows that the border pillars were approved by the government of Pakistan and Iran. On October 30, 1956, it was reported that a complete agreement had been reached regarding the delimitation of the borders of the two countries, which was officially approved and signed in February 1958. However, the implementation of the agreement was not published and was delayed until the establishment of a military regime in Pakistan in October 1958, after which it became a priority. The task of determining the line was completed by erecting border pillars on February 10, 1959, one year after the signing of the agreement.

The border agreement between Pakistan and Iran is a turning point in the history of Iran-Pakistan relations, so that the movement towards the federation of Iran, Afghanistan and Pakistan by the then president of Pakistan Iskandar Mirza (March 1956-October 1958) and Feroz Khan Noon (December 1958- October 1959) was done by the then prime minister. The Shah of Iran also showed great interest in the confederation plan (Louis Dupree, 1963: 388). After that, Ayub Khan proposed the integration of brother, neighboring and Muslim countries in a political unity on August 6, 1962. But Afghanistan prevented and showed that it is not ready to stop promoting Pashtunistan.

Iran and Pakistan concluded other agreements in the field of bilateral cooperation. On November 17, 1959, an agreement was signed in Tehran, which granted facilities to the citizens of Pakistan and Iran in terms of residence, possession, ownership and transfer of property and commercial assets in both countries. Also, an agreement was concluded regarding border management and fishing rights in border areas.

Following the Treaty of Amity and Resolution of Border Disputes, the Treaty of Extradition of Criminals and Accused was signed on April 20, 1959/April 30, 1960 A.H. by Ali Asghar Hekmat, Minister of Foreign Affairs of Iran and Nawabzadeh Agha Mohammad Reza, Grand Ambassador of the Republic of Pakistan. According to this treaty, in article 15, the two governments were obliged to hand over the person who is recognized as a criminal according

to the laws of the two countries and whose imprisonment is less than one year, to his country of origin. This agreement did not include the extradition of political and military criminals. Extradition costs up to the border are the responsibility of the extraditing government, the request for extradition is made through political channels, and documents such as a summary of the crime, the date of its occurrence, and a copy of the legal provisions to which the requesting country is subject, must be sent to the opposite country along with the application. Hand over This agreement was drawn up in Persian and English and its implementation period was five years (Ali Babayi, 2012: 117-119).

Regional tripartite agreement

The agreement between the three countries of Iran, Pakistan and Turkey was to create a free trade zone. It is referred to as "Regional Construction Cooperation."

Regional Construction Cooperation (RCD) 1964/1343 A.H

This cooperation is actually an economic agreement between the three countries of Iran, Turkey and Pakistan, the regional members of the Sento Agreement. In other words, the small states of the region defend their interests against the big powers in bilateral relations outside the international institutional framework. They can also develop regional institutions to protect their national interests. Based on this, the relations between Iran and Pakistan reached their peak when they entered into a regional construction cooperation agreement (RCD) with Turkey in 1964. Regional cooperation was to develop a tripartite agreement between Turkey, Iran and Pakistan for non-political and regional cooperation. The heads of state of Pakistan, Iran and Turkey met in a meeting in Istanbul and agreed to formulate a plan for regional cooperation and development of the RCD for peace, economic development and cultural progress. The need for such a regional agreement was strongly felt. While cooperation at the global level was mainly done through the United Nations and its agencies, it was felt that by organizing cooperation at the regional level, economic problems could be solved and immediate and quick results could be obtained. The three brotherly countries of Iran, Pakistan and Turkey already had a lot in common and joining a strong regional economic group was the most natural right and beneficial for the three countries. These three countries are neighbors and had many ancient historical ties. All of them are Muslim countries and were more or less in the same state of economic development and followed a similar foreign policy. They also had several years of experience working together under the supervision of Sento. The close and warm relations between Iran and Pakistan were expressed through their mutual participation in the Baghdad Pact.

The formation of RCD was considered very useful for the Shah of Iran and Ayub Khan to gain the support of their respective governments inside. Freedom from the United States was welcomed by the opposition party in both countries. Therefore, Yusuf Khatak, the leader of the opposition party in the National Assembly of Pakistan, called it a step in the right direction. (Pakistan National Assembly Debates, 1964, vol 3: 1212) In the meantime, the assembly announced that the members of the RCD would be able to escape from Sento. It was said that the staunch friends of the United States did not see the disadvantages of the friendship of the

United States. (The same) The reaction to the formation of the RCD in Tehran was also very favorable. Jafar Sharif Emami, the president of the Senate, described this union as a "political master", but emphasizing the non-political content of the agreement, he added: "I believe that there is a good place for Afghanistan in the union." (Dawn, 1964, July 29) Abdullah The Speaker of the Islamic Council, Mr. Riazi, said about this union, this union helps the development of member countries and world peace. (ibid) Hassan Ali Mansour, Prime Minister of Kurdistan, in his speech in Kurdistan, welcomed the decision of Iran, Pakistan and Turkey for closer cooperation as a great political, social, economic and cultural union consisting of 150 million Muslims. (ibid)

Ministers of economy and heads of planning and budget organizations and other high-ranking experts met each other in a conference in Ankara. In the aforementioned conference, the heads of the three countries expressed their opinion that regional cooperation is the main factor in accelerating national growth and development and ensuring peace and stability:

- 1) Establishing free exchange of goods by concluding commercial contracts
- 2) Establishing more relations and cooperation between existing chambers of commerce and establishing joint chambers of commerce
- 3) Improving the development of air transport lines within the region and establishing a well-equipped international airline between the three countries that can effectively compete with other airlines.
- 4) Studying the possibilities of developing a close cooperation in shipping
- 5) Carrying out necessary studies and investigations for the construction and improvement of road and railway communication lines between the three countries
- 6) Signing a contract to develop the tourism industry in the region
- 7) Technical assistance and cooperation with each other by sending technical staff training experts and scholarship exchanges between the three countries.

In this conference, it was also agreed that in order to coordinate construction plans, a regional planning council would be formed from the heads of the program organizations and other experts of the three member countries, and the secretariat of the regional construction organization would be established in Tehran.

Treaty of Baghdad/Sento 1955/1333 AH

One of the characteristics of the behavior of small powers is to have closer relations with a superpower or a great power to protect its security interests. David Vital called this behavior (pilot fish), that is, the whale's approach to avoid being eaten (David Vital, 1971: 33). Considering the geographical proximity of the Soviet Union to Iran and Pakistan, it seems logical that these two countries try to prioritize friendship with this country in their diplomatic relations. The change in Pakistan's policy occurred when the United States of America showed its disappointment with India after the Indian Prime Minister's visit to Washington in 1949. At the same time, Pakistan received an invitation for its prime minister to visit Moscow. A similar

invitation was later made by the United States. Pakistan Prime Minister Liaquat Ali Khan decided to go to the United States. It seems that two factors motivated this change of preferences; First, Pakistan may try to use the US government's disillusionment with India's involvement in the anti-communist alliance system to its advantage. Second could be the fact that the United States was technologically and economically far ahead of the Soviet Union in the late forties and early fifties. Therefore, the economic interests of the United States can be an important factor in the preference of Pakistan for Americans. This was later confirmed by the President of Pakistan, Ayub Khan (Ayub Khan, 1968: 8). After that, Iran rejected any rapprochement with the Soviet Union, and therefore, when the Baghdad Pact was concluded with the initiative of the United States, consisting of Iraq, Turkey, and England. Iran also became a member of this treaty. The Baghdad Pact was also one of these types of pacts, the military and economic cooperation between the member countries of this pact was to maintain independence and territorial integrity and help peace and security in the member countries, with the support and cooperation of the United States of America. The members of this treaty were Iran, Turkey, Pakistan and England, and the United States of America was an observer member. On March 5, 1333 AH equal to February 24, 1955, the bilateral cooperation agreement between the two countries of the Kingdom of Iraq and the Republic of Turkey was signed in Baghdad, and that is why it was called the Baghdad Pact.

The main articles of this treaty, which was signed in Baghdad between the representatives of Iraq and Turkey, were joined by Pakistan on September 22, 1956, and Iran on October 22, 1955.

It is explained: 1) the signatories of this agreement will cooperate with each other in their defense and security affairs, 2) the signatory countries undertake to avoid any interference in each other's internal affairs and to resolve the issues between them through peaceful means. 3) The agreements of the signatory countries of this agreement with other countries should not contradict these obligations. 4) The term of this agreement is 5 years and it is possible to extend it for another 5 years.

Since its early days, the Baghdad Pact was trying to gain credibility due to its vague mission and non-commitment by the member states. On July 14, 1958, when the Iraqi movement had started and later had nothing but failure, the Shah of Iran and Iskandar Mirza, the then leader of Pakistan, both went to Iraq to participate in the Baghdad Pact.

This was a worrying time for foreign officials. Shah Faisal was executed by pro-Soviet Iraqi republican revolutionaries. In the meantime, the fall of Shah Faisal and the complete inability of the governments of the Baghdad Pact or Washington to do anything about it was considered a daunting issue for other leaders of the Pact. In fact, this was a clear lesson, this was not a treaty they could rely on to maintain their domestic political sovereignty.

The Shah of Iran and the Pakistanis were still willing to give this pact a chance. On July 20, 1958, Mohammad Reza Shah met with Edward Thompson Wills, the American ambassador to Iran. During this period, the President of Pakistan, Iskander Mirza, was also in Tehran. According to Mohammad Reza Shah, both Iran and Pakistan were in favor of "coordinating efforts to eliminate the new revolutionary regime" in Iraq.

Iran, the Turkish government, as well as the Pakistanis publicly argued that intervening in Iraq to prevent a coup d'état would disrupt regional relations. Mohammad Reza Shah was also afraid of Turkey's unilateral intervention in Iraq, because in his opinion, this intervention would end up harming Iran. Iraq should correspond. He would have preferred the United States to lead this pact. This was an example of another trend of implicit competition among the members of the Baghdad Pact. A few years earlier, at the end of the Shah of Iran's visit to Washington in December 1954, the Shah asked Eisenhower to support the anti-Soviet forces in the region, and also asked Washington to balance The power demanded cooperation between Turkey, Iran and Pakistan. (Memorandum for the President, 1954: 87)

In 1959, the Iraqi leftist regime of Abdul Karim Qasim in Baghdad officially withdrew from the Baghdad Pact. And a few days later, with the transfer of its headquarters from Baghdad to Ankara, this pact was renamed to the Sento Pact. (Nazeef Kar and Norouzi, 2004: 186-195) and despite the name change and restart of that organization, it still suffered from the same previous symptoms.

Immediately after the fall of King Faisal in Baghdad and after Iraq withdrew from the Baghdad Pact, the United States acted quickly to prevent the collapse of the alliance. For this reason, in the meeting of the Council of Ministers of the remaining members, the United States decided that the remaining nations of the NATO should cooperate for the benefit of world peace, or in other words, the same as Article 5 of NATO, "An attack on one member is an attack on all members."

Ayub Khan, the commander of the Pakistani army during the presidency of Iskandar Mirza, has also mentioned this competition in his memoirs. He mentions an informal dinner in July 1958 with the presence of President Iskandar Mirza, the Shah of Iran and Turkish President Jalal Bayar. And discussed its dangers. (Ayub Khan, 1968: 179) These two issues were expressed by Khan:

The "paradoxical advantage" of the Baghdad Pact, as he put it, was that it strengthened collective defense, at least globally. The leaders of each country in the region knew that they had to rely on themselves or sign a bilateral security agreement with the United States, and anything else was pointless.

In any case, this pact was of little use as a political salvation, shortly after that the chaos in Baghdad recurred. And in the meantime, three months after the revolution in Iraq, Iskander Mirza was removed from power by a coup at the hands of Pakistan's military leaders, led by Field Marshal Ayub Khan.

Iranians and Pakistanis were ecstatic about this turn and hoped that this would mean an increase in American military and financial aid. However, paying more attention to the members of Cento was not the goal of the United States. Within six months, it became clear that Washington merely wanted to prevent the dissolution of the cento, but had no intention of writing a "blank" check to the remaining cento states. The US State Department submitted a memo to President Eisenhower on February 23, 1959, in which it was clearly acknowledged that Washington should remind Iran, Turkey, and Pakistan that the United States "had the same obligations" and

assumed in Article 1 of the Baghdad Pact they had done, will not take over. (Memorandum for the President, 1954: 79) This provision guarantees that the members will "cooperate for their own defense security" which led to the great disappointment of the United States to the members of CENTO, during the cooperation of this organization for 24 years.

Within SENTO, both these countries had the same approach on various issues. Only Pakistan and Iran insisted that a single command structure be imposed on the Sinto army. (S.M Burke, 1972: 171). This was probably because, while other SENTO members were also members of other defense alliances or had their own independent or bilateral defense arrangements, this was not the case with Iran or Pakistan, which were initially weak. Pakistan and Iran continued to cooperate under the supervision of Sento until Iran withdrew from it after the fall of the Pahlavi government in 1979.

CONCLUSION

Iran and Pakistan, having wide and common borders, have always played an important role in international and regional developments. Because during these years, the security needs and geographical location of two countries, Iran and Pakistan, have brought them closer to each other. Due to its proximity to India and of course for its own security, Pakistan tried to establish good relations with its neighbors, including Iran, in order to balance power against India. Therefore, in 1326/1947, Pakistan separated from India and formed an independent country with specific laws and policies. Accordingly, this country needed to have allies in the region and the world to strengthen its national security. Since Iran also took measures to strengthen its foreign relations with its neighbors. Pakistan was one of these countries that had political, commercial and cultural relations and agreements with Iran during the Pahlavi period, because Pakistan was one of America's regional allies in the Persian Gulf. Relations between Iran and Pakistan continued with some ups and downs until the end of the Pahlavi government and they maintained political relations at the highest level. In the political field, the conclusion of the friendship and cooperation agreement, the resolution of border disputes in the Sistan region, directed the relations of the two countries, this caused the close relations between the people of the two countries, so that the foreign relations and interactions between the two countries have an impact on the future of the relations between the two countries. It had a great influence internationally and regionally. Therefore, the available documents and reports show that since the beginning of the formation of the country of Pakistan until the fall of the Pahlavi monarchy in Iran, there were good political relations between Iran and Pakistan.

Sources and References

- 1) Amiri, Kiyomarth (1996): Persian language and literature in India. Tehran: Publications of the Council for the Development of Persian Language and Literature.
- 2) Burke, S.M. and Lawrence, Zairing (1999); History of Pakistan's foreign relations, translated by Iraj Vafaei, Tehran: Nasher Kavir.
- 3) Biruni, Abu Rayhan (1984); Research by Mallhand, translated by Manouchehr Sadoughi, Tehran: Bija.
- 4) Tasbihi, Mohammad Hossein (1974); Pakistani Farsi and Pakistani Studies, Bija: Rawalpindi.

- 5) Zunis, Marvin, (1992); *Shahane's Defeat*, translated by Abbas Mokhbar, Tehran: Man Ketab Publisher.
- 6) Zamaniyan, Ali Reza (2012); *Selected documents of Iran-Pakistan relations*, Tehran: Bureau of Political and International Studies.
- 7) *Yearbook of Iran's Foreign Relations (1974)*, Tehran: Ministry of Foreign Affairs.
- 8) Shafiei, Nozar (2007); "The roots and consequences of the conflict between religious forces and the government of Pakistan", *Hamshahri Diplomatic Monthly*, No. 16, Tehran: Hamshahri Institute.
- 9) Arefi, Mohammad Akram (2004); *The Islamic movement of Pakistan, investigation of the factors of failure in the establishment of the Islamic system of Qom*: Bostan Publications.
- 10) Ali Babaei, Gholamreza (2012); *The history of Iran-Pakistan relations from the independence of Pakistan to the Iranian revolution*, Tehran: Ministry of Foreign Affairs.
- 11) *Chronicle of fifty years of the Pahlavi dynasty (1986)*; Paris: Sohail.
- 12) Nazif Kar, Ghazaleh and Hossein Nowroozi (2012); *Strategic assessment of Pakistan*, Tehran: Publishing of Abrar Masazer Institute
- 13) Vaezi, Mahmoud (2010); "Iran and threats caused by instability in Afghanistan and Pakistan". *Journal of Crisis Centers in Asia*, Bija: Center for Strategic Research.
- 14) Hoshang Mahdavi, Abdul Reza (2019); *Iran's foreign policy (Pahlavi government 1980-1922)*, Tehran: Pikan Publishing.
- 15) Chaudhary, Shahid (1997); *History of Political Relations between Iran and Pakistan (Old Indus Valley), Persian Words in Urdu*, Tehran: Scientific and Cultural Publications.
- 16) Najafi Barzegar, Karim (2013); "Immigrants from Esfahani to the land of India (during the period of Jalal al-Din Muhammad Akbar)", *Literature and Languages*, No. 3, Bibai: Subcontinent.
- 17) Walian Abdulazim (1972); *Overview of the political, economic and social situation of Pakistan*: Zowar.

Documents

- 1) Organization of National Documents of Iran, Documents of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, No. 2/34: 1975
- 2) -----No. 129/P: 1958
- 3) ,-----No. 23/9: 1965
- 4) *Iran's Foreign Relations News and Documents, 1976-1974-1973-1972*, Tehran: Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

Newspapers

- 1) Information newspaper, 3/16/1:1950
- 2) Kayhan International, September 5, 1977
- 3) Dawn News, July 29, 1964
- 4) The news, October 24(2011)

Urdu Sources

- 1) Akram, Sheikh Mohammad (1968 AD); *Rood Karthar*, Lahore: Department of Islamic Culture, 2000-1987/Firooz Senses Limited.
- 2) Safdar, Mahmoud (1991 AD); *Ayin Pakistan*, Lahore, Jang Publishers.
- 3) Shahid Mukhtar, *Pakistan Min Fuji Government*, Lahore, Shahid Publishers, Nai Ta

Latin Sources

- 1) Ahmed, M. (2014). Ancient Pakistan-an archaeological history, Amazon
- 2) David Vital,(1971) survival of small states;studies in small power /great power conflict,n 9, oxford.
- 3) George Lenczowski, The Middle East in world affairs, London: Nd.
- 4) Jaun Romero,)2011(, The Iraqi Revolution of 1958: Revolutionary Quist for Unity and Security, University Press of America, Lanham .
- 5) Louis Dupree, (1963) A suggested Pakistan-Afghanistan-Iran Federation”, Middle East Journal,
- 6) autumn .
- 7) Memorandum for the President, February, (1954) Department of State,21-23.
- 8) Mohammad Ayub Khan, (1967) Frinds Not Masters, Lahore.
- 9) Mohammadally, S. S. (1979). Pakistan-Iran Relations (1947-1979). Pakistan Horizon, 32(4), 51-63.
- 10) Murtaza Rizvi, (1971) The Frontiers of Pakistan, Karachi.
- 11) Nazeer Ahmed Irani, (1977) Afjar-O-azaim, Islamabad.
- 12) Pakistan, G. O. (2016-17). Pakistan Economic Survey. Retrieved from http://www.finance.gov.pk/survey_1617.html
- 13) Pakistan National Assembly Debates, (1964) vol 3 part 2.
- 14) Qureshi, K. (1968) .Pakistan and Iran-A Study in Neighbourly Diplomacy. Pakistan Horizon.
- 15) Rafique,Najma, (2016)Prospects of Pakistan Iran relations, Strategic studies,vol 36 .
- 16) Scatter, Abdul. (2007), Pakistans foreign policy, Karachi, Oxford university press
- 17) S.M Burke,(1973) Pakistan’s foreign policy: An Historical Analysis (London:OUP).
- 18) Surender Chopra, (1974) Pak Afghan Relations, Indian Journal of Political Science, Vol 35, No 4.
- 19) Syed Sharifuddin Pirzada, (1969) Foundations of Pakistan All-India Muslim League Documents: 1906-1947, Vol 1 – 1906-1924, National Puclishing House Limited, Dacca.
- 20) The Imperial Gazetter of India,(1908) vol vii,Oxford.
- 21) united nations. (1962) Treaty series.
- 22) Vatanka, Alex (2015) Iran and Pakistan Security Diplomacy and American Influence, I.B. Tauris Uk
- 23) Zahid Ali Khan, (2004) Pakistan-Iran in Central Asia, Cooperation and conflicts, University of Blochistan, Quetta.